

SolarTwins-TEKPOL Pizza Seminars

TOGG and Beyond (in Turkish)

Theme: Energy, European Research Area and SSH Aspects

Arda Mevlütoğlu, Kubilay Yıldırım ve Semih Akçomak
Moderator: Erkan Erdil

Live Seminar Time and Date: 12:00-13:00 (Turkish time / GMT + 3)

Friday, April 15, 2022

Register at: <https://forms.gle/NLPQQYoayiZPLXGe7>

Moderation: Erkan Erdil

Registration for live seminar closes at 20:00, Thursday, 14 April 2022: To receive the link to the live seminar you must register by 20:00, Thursday 14 April 2022.

Abstract: In this panel the panelists will discuss the indigenous technology development attempt of Turkey delving in to the case of TOGG, Turkey's electric automobile that is planned to hit the roads by the end of 2022. The discussion will touch on hot debated topics such as the future of automobile and convergence of automobile sector to ICT and technology and innovation policy and the green deal.

Speakers:

Arda Mevlütoğlu: He holds a bachelor's degree from Istanbul Technical University Aerospace Engineering and a master's degree from METU Science and Technology Policy Studies. He is currently working as the assistant general manager responsible for defense programs in a consultancy and foreign trade firm.

Kubilay Yıldırım: He has a bachelor's degree in Mechanical Engineering from Middle East Technical University. He is currently working as a manager in a technology and engineering firm serving various manufacturing sectors, automotive and electrical mobility sectors.

Semih Akçomak: He holds BA and MA from Middle East Technical University, Department of Economics, and a PhD from Maastricht University, UNU-MERIT. He conducts research on science and technology policies and technology economics. He is the director of METU-TEKPOL and a faculty member at METU Science and Technology Policy Studies.

About SolarTwins-TEKPOL Pizza Seminars: The path to a prosperous, sustainable, and secure Turkey includes a Clean Energy Transition (CET) and Green Economy Transition (GET). Many of the largest challenges to be solved to realize these transitions lie at the intersection of technology and policy. Some of these challenges are unique to a specific technology, while others are cross-cutting challenges that underpin the competitiveness of Turkey's Research and Innovation (R&I) ecosystem. This SolarTwins-TEKPOL Pizza Seminar series aims to provide a scientific forum to increase awareness of these challenges and contribute to the co-creation of solutions to overcome these challenges. This series is designed as a part of SolarTwins Project Joint Research Line 9: Social Aspects of Sustainable Energy Transitions

About SolarTwins: SolarTwins is a European Union Horizon 2020 (H2020) project coordinated by ODTÜ-GÜNAM through METU with CIEMAT-PSA (Spain) and DLR (Germany) as partners. The objectives of the SolarTwins project are to

1. Step-up the scientific excellence of the Concentrating Solar Thermal (CST) Research Division ODAK of ODTÜ-GÜNAM through capacity building activities in collaboration with the globally leading CST institutions CIEMAT-PSA and DLR.
2. Strengthen METU, ODTÜ-GÜNAM, and Turkey's horizontal Research and Innovation (R&I) Capacities.

About METU TEKPOL: Science and Technology Policy Studies (STPS) program was founded in 1997 at the Middle East Technical University with the explicit objective to supply science and technology policy related human capital for the government bodies, agencies and other related organizations and to conduct research in science, technology and innovation policy issues. It has organic relations with the Research Center for Science and Technology Policies. Education and research elements integrate under METU-TEKPOL. TEKPOL is the only academic unit in Turkey that concurrently coordinates education and research activities. It operates M.Sc. and Ph.D. programs in science technology policy studies at the Graduate School of Social Sciences. TEKPOL also conducts interdisciplinary research on science and technology policy issues with the aim of addressing societal challenges.

PROGRAMME:

Date	Speaker, Institution	Seminar Title
15 April 2022	Arda MEVLÜTOĞLU, Kubilay YILDIRIM and Semih AKÇOMAK	TOGG and Beyond (in Turkish) - Panel
22 April 2022	Onur Çağdaş ARTANTAŞ	Promotion of Green Electricity: Legal and Political Perspectives (in Turkish)
29 April 2022	Serdar TÜRKELİ	Technological change and non-intervention, novel indicators and non-measurement (in Turkish)
13 May 2022	Barbel EPP	Cost Trends for Commercial and Industrial Solar Heat
20 May 2022	Pınar DERİN GÜRE	Gender and social sciences involvement in technology development projects in energy (in Turkish)
27 May 2022	Şuhnaz YILMAZ ÖZBAĞCI	TBA (in Turkish)
3 June 2022	Derek BAKER	ODAKTR: Concentrating Solar Thermal (CST) as a key enabling technology for Turkey's Clean Energy Transition.
10 June 2022	Christian OLTRA (CISOT)	Introducing SSH aspects of Energy Transitions
17 June 2022	Sara Banu AKKAŞ and Zelal ÖZDEMİR	METU in New European Research Area (in Turkish)
24 June 2022	Seven AĞIR	AgroPV Potential, Opportunities and Barriers in Turkey: A Preliminary Evaluation From Social Sciences Perspective (in Turkish)

Contact: Yelda ERDEN TOPAL
yeldae@metu.edu.tr

ERKAN ERDİL
erdil@metu.edu.tr

Derek K. BAKER
dbaker@metu.edu.tr

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